

Accurate Prediction of Violent Slosh Loads via a Weakly Compressible VoF Formulation

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ABSTRACT

The standard CFD scheme used today for the purpose of slosh loads predictions is based on an incompressible type volume of fluid (VoF) scheme. This however results in over-predicted pressure spikes and slow simulations due matrix conditioning in the case of violent slosh. In a recent review article Ibrahim (2020) further postulates the importance of accounting for gas compression in quantifying pressures due wave impact. We have therefore furthered the development of a novel weakly compressible ELEMENTAL[®] formulation for the accurate modelling of violent slosh loads. New developments include the introduction of a momentum conservative HiRAC VOF scheme as well as accounting for surface tension effects via higher order accurate height functions Ilangakoon et al. (2020). The developed modelling capability was proven via application to simulating two violent slosh experiments viz. lateral and verticle slosh in the presence of gravity. Particularly high accuracy was demonstrated, where the L2 error norm in the latter case was less than 2%. It was further shown that accounting for gas compressibility in a weak sense reduces predicted pressure peaks by up to 50% while the solver was 7 times faster to run. This is seen as a key development for more effective slosh impact design.

KEY WORDS: VoF; Weakly Compressible; Surface Tension; CSF; Height Functions.

INTRODUCTION

Violent slosh is of key concern to a range of applications due the high pressure loads involved. These range from ship tanker designs and aircraft fuel tanks to breakwater mitigation structures. The peak pressures due impacting waves remain a challenging phenomenon due it involving a range of interrelated physics. A recent seminal article devoted to this topic by Ibrahim (2020) postulates the importance of not only the liquid motion but also the compressibility of the gas. To date however incompressible VoF is the standard method for violent slosh simulations. This can result in the prediction of unrealistic pressure spikes and matrix ill conditioning (long solution times).

As such, we employed a weakly compressible formulation Heyns et al. (2013b) in this article in combination with the HiRAC Heyns et al. (2013a) compressive VoF interface capturing scheme. The citations however were limited in applicability to violent slosh due a non-conservative momentum implementation while accurate surface tension modelling was not employed. This is key particularly when Rayleigh-Taylor instability drives the mode of the first liquid impact as is the case with verticle slosh cases.

To address the cited shortcomings, this article describes a formulation for the accurate prediction of violent slosh related impact loads. The key components include a weakly compressible gas formulation (in conjunction with incompressible liquid), momentum conservative HiRAC and accurately accounting for surface tension via a recently developed higher-order surface tension formulation Ilangakoon et al. (2020). The resulting simulation framework is implemented into the ELEMENTAL[®] software and applied to modelling two violent slosh experimental benchmark test-cases. The first involves lateral excitation and the second verticle. High accuracy and computational efficiency were demonstrated.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The governing equations describe, for a weakly-compressible gas coupled with an incompressible liquid, the conservation of momentum, volume fraction and mass:

$$\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) + \rho \mathbf{a} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \alpha \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1 - \alpha}{\rho_g} \frac{1}{c_g^2} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{u} , p and \mathbf{a} are the fluid velocity, pressure and domain/tank acceleration. Further, c_g is the acoustic velocity for the gas phase. The fluid density and viscosity are represented by ρ and μ . For two phase modelling the VOF fraction is denoted α such that fluid properties ϕ is defined by

$$\phi = \alpha\phi_l + (1 - \alpha)\phi_g$$

where the l and g subscripts respectively denote liquid and gas phases. The closure equation involves the assumption of adiabatic or isentropic compression/expansion (adiabatic reversible) with the acoustic velocity being:

$$c_g^2 = \frac{\gamma_g P}{\rho_g}, \quad (4)$$

where for air $\gamma_g = 1.4$.

NUMERICAL SCHEME

We employed a fractional-split (pressure projection) method for the purpose of temporal discretization. This commences by computing the intermediate velocity \mathbf{u}^* from:

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \frac{1}{\rho^{n+1}} \left[\rho^n \mathbf{u}^n + \Delta t \left(-\nabla \cdot \rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u} \Big|_n + \nabla \cdot \mu \left(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T \right) \Big|_n + \rho \mathbf{g} \Big|_n \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

where n is last time-step solved for. The pressure for the weakly compressible system was next solved implicitly for the next time-step $n + 1$ from:

$$0 = \nabla \cdot \left(\mathbf{u}^* - \frac{\Delta t}{\rho^{n+1}} \nabla p^{n+1} \right) + \frac{(1 - \alpha^{n+1})}{\gamma \rho^{n+1}} \frac{p^{n+1} - p^n}{\Delta t} \quad (6)$$

which is non-linear in terms of p^{n+1} . Finally the velocity was computed at $n + 1$ via:

$$\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^* - \frac{\Delta t}{\rho^{n+1}} \nabla p^{n+1} \quad (7)$$

Spatial discretization was effected using a vertex-centered edge-based discretization scheme Ilangakoon et al. (2020). For surface tension computation purposes we employed a higher order method developed recently by Ilangakoon et al. (2020). This was key to accurately modelling vertical violent slosh which requires accounting for Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities.

For the discretisation of the momentum equation, a face α_f value must be supplied when discretizing for the nodal volume i . In Heyns et al. (2013a) this was the same face value computed from the semi-discretized HiRAC VoF equation:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_i}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{V_i} \sum_{f \in \partial \Omega_i} \alpha_f \mathbf{u}_{ff} + \nabla \cdot \alpha(1 - \alpha) \mathbf{u}_{hr} = 0,$$

where \mathbf{u}_{ff} is the dot product between the fluid velocity and volume face coefficient (face area multiplied by outward pointing unit normal) and \mathbf{u}_{hr} is defined below. This however does not lead to a conservative momentum discretization which becomes problematic when simulating violent slosh.

We therefore propose a conservative formulation by equating the above

to the spacial component of the volume fraction continuity equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \alpha' \mathbf{u} &= \nabla \cdot \alpha \mathbf{u} + \nabla \cdot \alpha(1 - \alpha) \mathbf{u}_{hr} \\ \frac{1}{V_i} \sum_{f \in \partial \Omega_i} \alpha'_f \mathbf{u}_{ff} &= \frac{1}{V_i} \sum_{f \in \partial \Omega_i} \alpha_f \mathbf{u}_{ff} + \alpha_f (1 - \alpha_f) c_\alpha \frac{|\mathbf{u}_{ff}|}{A_f} \frac{|\nabla \alpha^*|}{|\nabla \alpha^*|_f} \cdot A \hat{\mathbf{n}}_f \\ &= \frac{1}{V_i} \sum_{f \in \partial \Omega_i} \left(\alpha_f + \alpha_f (1 - \alpha_f) c_\alpha \frac{\text{sign}(u_{ff})}{A_f} \frac{|\nabla \alpha^*|}{|\nabla \alpha^*|_f} \cdot A \hat{\mathbf{n}}_f \right) \mathbf{u}_{ff}, \\ \therefore \alpha'_f &= \alpha_f \left(1 + (1 - \alpha_f) c_\alpha \frac{\text{sign}(u_{ff})}{|\nabla \alpha^*|} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_f \right), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where α'_f is the new momentum conservative face volume fraction. Further, $c_\alpha = 0.1$ while A and $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_f$ are respectively the volume face and related outward pointing normal unit vector.

HIRAC VALIDATION

A number of metrics were used to determine the performance of a VoF advection scheme. The shape or geometric error, which measures the absolute difference between the analytical and numerical solution at a given node, is expressed as

$$\varepsilon_g(\mathbf{x}_i, t) = |\alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_i, t) - \alpha_a(\mathbf{x}_i, t)|,$$

where $\varepsilon_g(\mathbf{x}_i, t)$ is the error at time t and \mathbf{x}_i is the node coordinate. The numerical and analytical values of the volume fraction are denoted α_n and α_a respectively. The analytical volume fraction field is computed in this work by using AGI Jones et al. (2019).

The L_1 norm of the geometric error was computed,

$$\|\varepsilon_g\|_1 = \int_{\Omega} \varepsilon_g dV = \sum_i V_i \varepsilon_g(\mathbf{x}_i),$$

where V_i is the dual cell volume associated with node i . To determine the boundedness of the volume fraction a bounding error ε_b is introduced as

$$\varepsilon_b = \max_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{X}_{\Omega}} (0, \max(0, \alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_i) - 1), \max(0, -\alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_i))).$$

Volume conservation was assessed as follows via

$$\varepsilon_v = \frac{|\sum_i V_i \alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_i, t_m) - \sum_i V_i \alpha_a(\mathbf{x}_i, t_0)|}{\sum_i V_i \alpha_a(\mathbf{x}_i, t_0)},$$

where ε_v represents the volume error and t_0 and t_m represent the initial and final state of the volume fraction field respectively.

Shear Flow

The shear flow test case, proposed by Rider and Kothe Rider & Kothe (1998), subjects a 2D circular interface to large shear flows in a smooth velocity field. Due to the convoluted interface motion this tests many of the sub-components of a VoF scheme. The circular drop or bubble of radius $r = 0.15$ was placed with its centre half way along the domain's x -axis and three quarters along the y -axis, where the domain was of unit size. An analytical time varying shear velocity was applied to the domain and was given by

$$\mathbf{u}(x, y, t) = \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(2\pi y) \sin^2(\pi x) \cos\left(\frac{\pi t}{t_m}\right) \\ -\sin(2\pi x) \sin^2(\pi y) \cos\left(\frac{\pi t}{t_m}\right) \end{bmatrix},$$

where $t_m = 8\text{s}$ and is the time domain. At the half way mark, where $t = 4\text{s}$, the velocity field reverses direction and by t_m the volume fraction field *should* have returned to its original position.

Figure 1 depicts a zoomed in portion of the final volume fraction field plot for the structured 256^2 mesh as computed by CICSAM (on which

Fig. 1 Volume fraction field plots CICSAM (left) and HiRAC (right) at $t = 8s$ on the finest structured mesh.

Table 1 Comparative error results for a disc in shear flow for the formulated CICSAM and HiRAC schemes on a structured Cartesian mesh for $c_f = 0.5$. In the table N denotes the number of nodes in each axis direction while the other symbols are defined above.

Scheme	$N^{\frac{1}{2}}$	ε_v	ε_b	ε_g	$\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon_g)$
CICSAM	64	3.34e-15	3.14e-34	7.61e-02	-
HiRAC	64	5.89e-16	2.00e-45	2.41e-02	-
CICSAM	128	3.08e-14	9.38e-59	3.90e-02	0.963
HiRAC	128	3.06e-14	4.47e-46	4.66e-03	2.370
CICSAM	256	1.77e-15	1.98e-69	5.53e-03	2.820
HiRAC	256	2.08e-14	1.53e-14	1.39e-03	1.749
CICSAM	512	1.77e-13	1.18e-99	9.06e-04	2.608
HiRAC	512	1.26e-14	9.81e-12	6.44e-04	1.106

HiRAC is based) as well as HiRAC. This provides a clear picture of the significant increase in accuracy achieved showing that both the two-phase interface is sharper and that the bulk of tracked phase consistency maintains a volume fraction above 0.99.

Tables 1 and 2 present the qualitative results obtained from the test case on both structured and unstructured meshes. The bounding errors, ε_b are within machine precision tolerances. Particularly on structured meshes, HiRAC offers a significant improvement in accuracy as compared to CICSAM.

VIOLENT SLOSH MODELLING

Here we compared a 2D simulation in ELEMENTAL[®] to measured data from an experiment performed by the University of Bristol, and described in Oxtoby et al. (2015). In the experiment, a baffled tank was filled to 75% by volume with water and then shaken sinusoidally in the horizontal direction, inducing a violent sloshing flow in the tank. There are pressure probes on opposite tank walls, recording slosh-induced pressures during the tank excitation. The differential pressure in the tank measured by these probes were then compared to simulation using both incompressible and weakly compressible formulations. No-slip conditions were applied to all boundaries and Newtonian air and water viscosities assumed.

Table 2 Comparative error results for a disc in shear flow for the formulated CICSAM and HiRAC schemes on an unstructured triangular mesh for $c_f = 0.5$.

Scheme	$N^{\frac{1}{2}}$	ε_v	ε_b	ε_g	$O(\varepsilon_g)$
CICSAM	64.016	7.85e-16	3.36e-27	4.22e-02	-
HiRAC	64.016	3.93e-15	7.50e-29	3.18e-02	-
CICSAM	128.012	2.16e-15	4.49e-34	6.16e-03	2.777
HiRAC	128.012	5.89e-16	3.29e-36	6.76e-03	2.233
CICSAM	255.996	1.85e-14	1.46e-47	1.57e-03	1.970
HiRAC	255.996	1.94e-14	2.57e-46	1.51e-03	2.167
CICSAM	511.996	6.05e-14	7.16e-66	4.68e-04	1.749
HiRAC	511.996	2.93e-14	9.89e-67	4.44e-04	1.762

Fig. 2 Screenshot showing the tank with a sloshing flow of the liquid (red) at the top and a zoom of the mesh around the baffle opening at the bottom.

The mesh used for the simulation is presented in Fig. 2 and contains 10,571 computational nodes on a hybrid, unstructured mesh. Reference fluid properties are water and air at normal temperature and pressure (NTP). Comparison of the tank differential pressure evolution for incompressible and weakly compressible simulations to experiment is shown in Fig. 4. Considering the entire time spectrum, a good comparison is achieved. We observe that the weakly compressible formulation does not contain the many excessive artificial pressure spikes as seen for the incompressible simulation. The weakly compressible simulation is also much more efficient, requiring 7 times less CPU time as compared to the incompressible simulation (note that the number of time-steps required were near identical).

The final test-case involved verticle slosh due damped sinusoidal oscillation under gravity conditions. The experimental data produced by the European Union Horizon 2020 SLOWD Protospace test campaign enables such an evaluation of the CFD software to occur by utilising the experimental acceleration profiles and comparing the simulated and experimental slosh loads. No-slip conditions were applied to all boundaries and Newtonian air and water viscosities assumed. To enable correct modelling of the involved Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities, the initial surface meniscus was initiated through solving the differential equation:

Fig. 3 Zoom at early time of the normalized pressure differential between tank walls compared to experiment.

Fig. 4 Normalized pressure differential of the entire excitation cycle.

$$\frac{\sigma}{\rho g_y} \frac{\partial^2 \eta_0}{\partial x^2} = \eta_0 \left[1 + \left(\frac{\partial \eta_0}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (9)$$

where η_0 is the liquid elevation above the surface and x is the distance from the tank wall. The boundary conditions are

$$\frac{\partial \eta_0}{\partial x} = \pm c \cot(\theta) \text{ at } x = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \eta_0 = 0 \text{ as } \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty}$$

To assess mesh independence of the solution, we employed the experimental acceleration profile for various structured meshes where

Fig. 5 Points of interest for the SLOWD Protospace Simulations

Fig. 6 Verticle slosh case: Predicted vs. measured total verticle slosh force.

Fig. 7 Mesh Independence Study for Simulated Vertical Slosh Loads. The red line denotes the normlised L2 difference between computed and measured tank forces while the blue line is added to show asymptotic convergence.

$\Delta x = \Delta y$. Fig. 6 provides a comparison of the vertical slosh force for various mesh sizes against the experimentally measured force. The high acceleration encountered leads to non-linear and violent sloshing as seen if Fig. 5b and Fig. 5c. The rotational movements within the protospace system resulted in early fluid impact for the compartments at the beam

tip, as seen in Fig. 5b.

The mesh refinement study conducted involved several grid resolutions, and a high degree of mesh independence was achieved. Predicted vs. experimental results for two of the meshes are shown in Fig. 6. Note that the higher error on the coarsest mesh was due to asymptotic convergence not having yet been achieved. The results of the mesh refinement study are shown in Table 3. As shown, the L2 error of predicted vs. experimental results are circa 1.2%, demonstrating exceptional accuracy.

Table 3 Error analysis of Protospace simulation where $\|\epsilon\|_1$ and $\|\epsilon\|_2$ are respectively the normalised L2 and L1 difference between simulated and measured loads (normalisation using the maximum measured force).

Δx	$\ \epsilon\ _1$ (%)	$\ \epsilon\ _2$ (%)
1×10^{-3}	17.529	1.2191
6.67×10^{-4}	17.413	1.2106
5×10^{-4}	17.332	1.2099
4×10^{-4}	17.2928	1.2092

CONCLUSIONS

We presented a weakly compressible two-phase modelling capability for computing violent slosh loads. To ensure accuracy of the interface a conservative HiRAC implementation was developed while surface tension was modelled via a higher order accurate formulation. Rigorous accuracy assessment was achieved by simulating two industrial strength violent slosh cases. It was demonstrated that the proposed weakly compressible formulation was devoid of most non-physical pressure spikes resulting from a pure incompressible formulation. In addition, exceptional mesh independence and accuracy was achieved., which is a key development for more effective slosh impact design.

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